

Management Impact on Insurance Companies

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study to investigate the most critical factors that affect the performance of insurance companies. Data collected from the annual reports published by Lahore Stock Exchange Pakistan during 2007-2016. Overall results show that claim ratio is significantly negatively related to return on assets, market-to-book ratio, return on equity and underwriting profit. Management is the backbone of any firm. The performance of a firm will be degraded without management. Management expenses are also significantly negatively impact on assets, return on equity and underwriting profit. The market faces a high level of risk, but with better manage risk will be converted to maximize profit and reduce the chances of losses. Management is as vital as blood for the human body. Without management, no companies whether a nation or multinational, can't progress.

Management and GDP growth rate go hand by the hand of any company. The performance of insurance companies depends on GDP because GDP reflects economic activity. GDP can only grow by the investment that is invested by stake-holder, shareholder *etc.* economic activity is a way to gain interest rates on different opportunities. The interest rate generally increases with opportunity cost which also reflects the return on assets, investment, income and market-to-book ratio. With proper management, the aforementioned tools can help the companies to ensure maximum profit and it also prevents investors from significant losses. To sum up, the finding of the study suggests that firms need to invest in management activities, workshops to enhance the profits of insurance companies in Pakistan.

Keywords— Profit margin; Claim ratio; Firm performance; GDP; Management performance; Pakistan

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's risky and dynamic business environment, no company can carry out its operations without the support of insurance companies. What is more, if insurance companies stop providing insurance, companies can stop their operations because of the risk. While insurance companies manage the risk of business entities or individuals, they are known as The Backbone of the Economy. From there, measuring the performance of insurance companies is of great importance for government, management, investors and image. The performance of the insurance company can be measured at the basis of various factors such as profitability, transaction sales, dividend growth, capital, employment and many others [1]. There are three types of factors that can affect the performance of insurance companies [2]. First, micro-factors is commonly known as reliable specific factors such as liquidity, age and size, etc. Secondly, there are some meat factors, such as

regulators, research institutions, and government roles. Finally, there are macroeconomic factors such as GDP, inflation and interest rates.

However, no study has been carried out to examine the joint effects of concrete and macroeconomic variables on the performance of insurance companies in Pakistan. For example, a study for research into Pakistan's executive insurance companies [3]. They noted that size and risk are positive, but the impact is negatively related to the performance of life insurers. The general insurance company data to examine the effects of size, investment, impact, risk, past performance, and age on ROA and Ro. Results and years are positive, while the impact and risk are negatively related to results [4]. Other studies in Pakistan represent only reliable concrete factors and completely ignore the role of macroeconomic factors. Therefore, this study aimed to fill the gap in the literature by examining the impact of solid concrete and macroeconomic factors on the performance of insurers in Pakistan.

In 1948, the government established the Security Department and gave it to the Department of Commerce to see all activities of the security sector. In 1949, to improve the security activity of the Pakistani government in the 9th century. The goal was to protect the rights and interests of its members and to support their business. To strengthen the government's insurance sector, Pakistan Her insurance Company (is now on the day, the Pakistani insurance company LTD) to provide an insurance facility for insurance companies. The government has taken further steps to develop the insurance sector and the number of companies reached 47 in 1971, which was 26. In 1973, the government established a state insurance company to enter the insurance industry and keep an interest in political guards. The government of 1973 replaced NCS with the National Investment Fund (NIF) to manage security and semi-public enterprises. NIF reduced the premium and transferred all proceeds to the Treasury government. In addition to securing more support for insurance and lowering costs, the government established a National Insurance Corporation (the United States, the National Insurance Company LTD) in 1976. semi-government in 1980, and the government of 1990 encouraged investment in the insurance sector.

The year 2000 has brought about many changes in the security sector in Pakistan; The first security sector was given to their security and exchange of Pakistan (SECP), to deal with the problems of the security industry in Pakistan. Secondly, a 1938 safety decision is outdated and replaced by other regulations. The new security is over on December 19. August 2000 of the SECP, which increased the minimum wage of capital requirements for life and damage insurance and results in an excellent financial health enterprise. The minimum capital paid for life insurance is 100 to 150 million rupees and 50 to 80 million rupees for a no-

life insurance company. Besides, the regulatory responsibilities of the insurance companies were transferred in 2002. Previously, the Ministry of Commerce was a foreign ministry [5].

On the other hand, the life sector has reached RS. 63. A stake in the Pakistani insurance sector in the world reached 0.02% World Security Report, 2010. The capitalization of the market sector in Pakistan was 224 billion in 2009. The statistics, therefore, show that changes in regulation and government measures have significantly contributed to the development of the Pakistani insurance sector. In Pakistan, the insurance sector is divided into two types, life insurance and insurance companies. Life insurance sectors have two main areas: group and individual security. Part of individual life insurance is more compared to group security. General safety does business in various areas, such as Marines, aviation, fire and real estate, motor insurance and poor. Part of car insurance is over 49% which is the largest and the other is not. Life insurance is less compared to non-life insurance. Private companies largely dominate the social security sector; they represent an 82% stake. The top ten companies have a stake of 79%. Moreover, of those ten EFU generals and the security of the Adama, 65% have an interest in the entire private sector [6]. The insurance industry in Pakistan has gained popularity in recent decades. Their share increases as a job, and the individual knows the importance of risk management. So the growth rate is rising among the insurance companies, but premium growth is falling. The two primary sources of insurance are premium and investment income. Investments are a percentage of total funds, while the use of the revenue generation decreases overtime. In the forest, facts are explained for the background and a pattern of insuring cases in Pakistan. There are now 3 lives and 20 non-life insurance companies listed on the Lahore Stock Exchange.

2. MOTIVATIONS

A large part of Empirical research in business performance has shut down financial companies from their analysis, as their decisions are a product of different regulations. For example, it pays less attention to financial companies (general) and insurance companies (especially) for an excellent reason for the effects of variables (micro and macro) on the performance of insurance companies in Pakistan Browse.

This study used data on life insurance and non-life insurance companies because both types of companies are part of the insurance industry.

There are three types of factors that may affect the performance of insurance companies (e.g., micro factors, meat factors and macro factors) based on the availability of data this study examines the effects of micro- and macro variables since there are no studies. However, We have looked at the joint effects of these variables.

1. Management: The results of this study support managers to understand the effects of Mirko and the macro factor on the performance of insurers in Pakistan.

2. Supervisory authorities: The results of these studies support regulatory authorities in shaping the Law on Improving the Performance of Insurance Companies in Pakistan.

3. Investors: The results of this study provide support to investors to understand the effects of the solvent, the growth of gross written premium and insurance claims, etc., affects the performance of insurance companies in Pakistan.

The rest of the paper is built as follows: Chapter 3 describes the methodology. Chapter 4 produces experimental results. Chapter 5 describes the literature review. Finally, Chapter 6 of the investigation has been concluded.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study aims to examine the key factors that affect the performance of insurance companies listed in Lahore in 2007-2016. For the assessment of the data collected from the annual reports provided by insurance undertakings during the study period. Data were relevant to the market price of shares collected from the publications of the Lahore stock exchange. Besides, data on macroeconomic variables such as GDP and interest rates are derived from the websites of the World Bank and the State Bank of Pakistan (SBP). Initially, all insurance companies included in the formula were included in the sample. However, the insurance companies did not have complete data on the variables in the study deleted from the analysis. Besides, a year of data is lost as a result of the increase in gross written premiums. The last sample consists of 23 companies for nine years. The specified sample is listed in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 SAMPLE SPECIFICATION

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Insurance Sector</i>	<i>No. of companies</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1	Life Insurance	3	18.18%
2	Non-life Insurance	20	81.82%
<i>Total</i>		23	100%

Table 3.2 is the definition of the variables in the study. Definitions have been mainly taken over by comparing the existing literature with previous empirical studies.

Table 3.2 DEFINITION OF VARIABLE

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Proxy</i>	<i>Definition</i>
Dependent variable		
<i>Return on assets</i>	ROA_{it}	The ratio of profit before tax to total assets
<i>Return on equity</i>	ROE_{it}	The ratio of profit before tax to shareholders equity
<i>Investment income</i>	INP_{it}	The ratio of investment income to net premium
<i>Underwriting profit</i>	UWP_{it}	The ratio of underwriting profit to net premium
<i>market-to-book ratio</i>	MBR_{it}	The ratio of market price per share to book value per share
Independent vari-		

able		
Claim ratio	$CLMR_{it}$	The ratio of net claims to net premium
Management expense	$MEXPN_{it}$	The ratio of management expense to net premium
Growth of gross written	$GROW_{it}$	Percentage change in gross written premium
Size	SIZ_{it}	Natural log of total assets
Age	AGE_{it}	Log of age. Age is computed by taking the difference
GDP	$GDPG_t$	The growth rate of GDP
Interest rate	INT_t	Rate of 12 months T-bills

The study used panel data to estimate regression models to identify the relationship between business-specific factors, macroeconomic factors, and the performance of insurers. Panel data are cross-sectional data or panel data that observations economic enterprises over time. Panel regression can alleviate measurement problems caused by lost or undetectable variables, and the results are therefore more reliable than the transverse and time-series data itself. To assess the effects of explanatory variables, use the combined ordinary minimum square. The basic regression model is expressed as follows:

$$r_{it} = \mu_{it} + F\{Z_t, X_t\}$$

In this model r_{it} , the profitability of the company i in year t represents a vector of the company's specific variables i in year t and Z_t is a vector variable that represents macroeconomic factors in year t . While μ_{it} error term.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 shows the aggressor statistics of variables included in the study. The average return on assets is 5.99%, indicating a share of pre-tax profit in total assets. The average return on equity is 17.11%, indicating a share of pre-tax income in shareholders. The average value of investment income is 27.31%, indicating a proportional ratio of the profits made by insurance companies from their investment activities. The average value of undervalued profitability is 24.01%, indicating the relative profit received by insurance companies through the main activities. The average ratio between market books is 2.71, indicating that insurance managers have created a higher value of their assets than the value of the books. The average benefit ratio is 39.98%, indicating the percentages of these companies were satisfied during the study period. This ratio is quite high, which can be caused by natural disasters (e.g., earthquakes and floods) or due to the inefficiency of managers during the study period. The average value of management costs is 28.97%, which indicates the share of management costs. The average collateral value is 62.01%, which is high and suggests that insurers are doing more damage to make

them safer. The current resource ratio is available to the company to meet current requirements. The average care is 2.01, indicating that insurance companies can settle claims in unforeseen situations such as natural disasters and the sudden fall in share prices on the market. The average increase in gross premiums is 14.23%. The average company size is 19,242. The average value of the year is 1,325. Finally, average GDP growth and interest rates are 3.981%.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

The ratio of complaints is positive and strongly linked to investment income while negatively linked to shareholders, underlying earnings and the relationship between the market and the books. Moreover, the ratio of the receptive negative is related to the return on assets. Management costs are negatively related to asset recovery, return on equity, profit index and receivable ratio. Although it is negatively linked to the relationship between the market and the books and the positively related investment income and relationship is negligible. The merger is positive and has an important impact on the relationship between returns, revenues and investment requirements. Although negative and significantly related to profit writing and the relationship between the market and books. Collateral damage is negatively related to the capital return and management, and the relationship is negligible. Liquidity is positively associated with investment income and management. Besides, it is positively linked to the return on assets, return on equity and the merger. On the other hand, it is negatively linked to profit revenue, the relationship between market books and recipients, and the relationship is negligible. Marge is positively linked to investment income, management costs, collateral and liquidity. It is also positively linked to the return of real estate, but the relationship is negligible. This is also negatively linked to the sub-writing of profits and the relationship between market books. It is also negatively linked to a return to capital, but the relationship is negligible. Gross premium growth is positively linked to the recovery of assets, return on equity, crediting profits and liquidity. Positively related to the market relationship with accounting, management costs, insurance and margins, but the relationship is negligible. On the other hand, it is negatively linked to the relationship between investment income and receivables, but this relationship is only significant with the relationship between claims. Size is positively linked to return on investment, return on investment, the relationship between market books and admission examples. It is also positively linked to asset recovery and the underwriting of profit, but the relationship is negligible. On the other hand, it is negatively related to management costs and racial margins. It is also negatively linked to collateral, liquidity and size, but the relationship is negligible. The years have been positively linked to wages and interest rates. It is also positively linked to the return on assets, return on equity, return on investment, claims and cost control, but the relationship is negligible. Negative related to profit gains, the relationship between market books and liquidity. It is also negatively linked to the growth of gross written premiums and sizes. GDP growth is positively related to asset recovery, return on equity, return on investment and gross written premium growth. It is also positively linked to endorsing profit and liquidity, but the relationship is negligible. Negatively related to the relationship of the market book, the relationship of claims, management costs, insurance,

margin, size and age, and the relationship is negligible. Interest rates are negatively related to asset recovery, return on equity, investment income, gross written growth and GDP growth. It is also negatively linked to the market-book ratio, recipients and liquidity, but the relationship is negligible. on the other hand, it is positively related to management, insurance, mark and payment costs, but the relationship is negligible.

Table 4.1 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Variables	Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	maximum
ROA_{it}	150	0.06	0.12	-0.80	0.53
ROE_{it}	150	0.17	0.32	-1.59	2.3
INP_{it}	150	0.23	0.39	-0.91	2.43
UWP_{it}	150	0.24	0.25	-0.35	1.10
MBR_{it}	150	2.31	3.99	0.00	34.10
INT_t	150	10.6	1.91	7.99	14.12
AGE_{it}	150	1.51	0.31	0.71	2.1
SIZ_{it}	150	22.1	1.50	19.11	25.12
$GROW_{it}$	150	0.21	0.31	-0.71	1.31
$GDPG_t$	150	3.99	2.31	1.71	8.01

5. RELATED WORK

Although little work has been done on the performance of the insurance sector, there is much work to be done in the banking sector, some authors have tried to conduct and modify these studies on the insurance sector. There are two factors of decisive, internal and external factors in these investigations. Internal factors control management and external factors beyond control. Organizational performance has taken cautious attention in the field of corporate financial literature [7]. However, in the context of the insurance sector, it has received little attention, so it is reasonable to research this area. The business performance has attracted the attention of corporate finance over the past decade but has given little attention to the insurance sector. Many factors want to take the importance of looking at the insurance sector. Consumers and investors are interested in knowing the results of insurance companies because they have invested and wanted to know how many companies have the right to return them or to meet the ongoing obligations of insurance policyholders. In Tunisia, the same study was done on life insurance companies in 2016 over eight years (2007-2014). The result of regression on the boards shows that age and first-class growth are essential measures for the performance of insurance companies measured by ROA. However, performance is not statistically significant in favor, inefficiency, liquidity, and risk [8].

This is the main objective of financial management, which increases the profitability of the company, indicating better results

for the company. Profitability is, therefore, an essential objective of financial management. Insurance undertakings provide facilities for the transfer of risks from one entity to another. It shows how insurers help the economy share and the risk transfer that can help in a precarious situation. Meanwhile, like other financial institutions, insurers play the role of a financial broker to channel financial resources from one to the other [9]. According to, the insurance industry plays a crucial role in stabilizing the economy [7]. The fuses operate in such a beautiful way that promotes financial and social stability, a rescue facility, supports trade and trade. They encourage entrepreneurs by having their own risk of entering and doing business in the market. They focus on the concept of quality improvement of life and overall progress. According to the nature of the company, we can classify the insurance sector into two types of life and non-life insurance (general insurance). Both differ in terms of operations, activities and investments and policies that they represent. Insurance companies act as financial intermediaries, while non-life insurers are at risk of absorbing the risk to other entities [10].

The company's performance plays an essential role in the growth of the industry-leading to economic success [11]. This study attempts to examine the financial results of Indian life insurance based on different parameters. The different ratios were used to calculate the results. They are solvency, profitability and income. Between 2007-2011-2012, 800 life insurance companies were used as samples and five-year data. Several linear models have been used to measure the extent to which these fortifications affect the performance of insurers. The results show that it is positively linked to liquidity and size, although it is negative with capital and has no connection with pay and leverage.

The robust, specific profitability factors of insurance companies are those under management control. Internal decisions are therefore those that affect the decisions of the administration [7]. There are two types of company-specific cuts, financial statements and non-accounting. The variables in the financial statements are those presented directly in the company's profit and loss account, balance account and financial statements. However, non-financial variables are not directly provided by the financial statements Presented. Size, impact, liquidity, tangent, growth and capital volume form part of the financial statements and financial statements [12]. Although financial variables are not management efficiency, no employees and industries, age, productivity and quality [13].

The claims are the price of an insurance company they paid to the police. High conditions are bad for the company's health and lead to insolvents. The claims have a negative effect on the profitability of insurers. This is in line with the microeconomic theory that the value of price increases reduces the company's profitability [14]. The action rate is expressed as net claims for net premiums. The damage on the lower damage shows the effectiveness of the insurance team and better manage claims and vice versa. Private companies have a better structure of infringement management compared to public companies, and this situation is favorable due to the low retention rate in the private sector and the high-risk policy that ceases. The same negative significant results for claims were found in the study of the financial performance of life insurance in Ghana [2].

Administrative expenses include operating expenses, including management wages and services, office, sampling, and ad-

ministrative expenses. This ratio is calculated as administrative costs plus commissions for net premiums. This relationship speaks of productivity and the cost of business efficiency. The lower ratio shows that the company is in good health and profitable. On the other hand, a higher percentage indicates financial instability. The higher operating costs have a direct impact on the profits of insurers and therefore, the collateral wants to reduce the number of their administrative costs. So, there is a difference between this variable and the profitability of insurance companies [15]. The authors found a negative link between administrative costs and general profitability and positive returns for investments in measuring 'the financial performance of Ghanaian life insurance companies. Administrative costs reduce the overall profitability of insurance but increase investment income because it affects the capacity of insurers who can identify and invest in profitable portfolios.

The increase in gross premiums is only the percentage increase in written premiums (sales). It is measured as a year-on-year change in insurance premiums. A horrible relationship found between rough and Indian life insurance [16]. This means that insurance companies that have higher growth will have lower profitability due to their attachment to rudeness and high risk of writing. The same result found that premium growth had a negative relationship in their insurance market study to identify key performance provisions between 2008 and 2012 [17]. The authors researched life insurance companies in Ghana to analyze performance [2]. The data were collected for the period 2000-2010 and the performance of insurance companies was measured based on three performance benchmarks; profitability, partial depreciation of profitability and investment income. The results show that the gross written premium has a significant positive link to the sale of profitability and the failure to confirm profit, but negative with investment income. Besides, in Pakistan found that gross written premium growth had a statistically insignificant relationship with the performance and profitability of insurance companies in Pakistan [2].

Larger companies are more profitable because they achieve economies of scale and come at the expense of staff. Besides, larger insurers have more capacity to deal with market volatility and uncertainty than smaller ones. The talent pool of large companies is growing more trained, skilled, experienced and qualified staff. In short, large companies are better at the worst situation than in smaller companies. The size of the company is measured as a natural log rhythm of the total funds [13]. Alternatively, according to [17], larger companies have a negative relationship with the results due to internal politics and bureaucratic decisions. While in Pakistan [3][5][7][18] found a positive relationship between the size and profitability of insurance companies in Pakistan.

The age of the company is measured by the annual company founded in the current year. Several researchers have found a positive relationship with insurance results. This is because older companies have a good market feeling and experience in solving problems and solving various uncertain situations in the market. Besides, older companies have more experience, skills and skills; they enjoy the latest learning and superior performance [14]. On the other hand, according to negatively related to performance [19]. In infidelity, it shows that older companies are prone to inertia and a bureaucratic structure that makes them

inflexible, and that is the biggest obstacle to the performance of insurers.

As mentioned earlier, there are external factors that affect the performance of insurers. Internal factors are discussed and external factors are macroeconomic and industrial factors. Interest rates, GDP, GDP growth, inflation, and unemployment are factors that can affect the insurer's performance and are used by various authors to measure the performance of insurance companies such as [2][14][20].

The rate of GDP growth increases the income level of people who increase purchasing power, leading to an increase in purchasing power. When people's purchasing power increases and they have money to invest, then the level of premiums are written for insurance companies versus that people need more insurance policies. Other policies mean more unattainable profits, which are generally in overall profitability. Therefore, GDP has a positive relationship. According to the authors, GDP growth has a positive effect on the performance of insurance companies [14]. This growth in the overall economy drives demand for insurance policies that indirectly lead to higher incomes.

The interest rates have a positive effect on insurers' performance because when interest rates rise, insurers benefit from their investments in short-term value companies and make healthy profits. As a result of interest rate changes, the interest rate risk relates to the company's profitability/performance [2]. Interest rates simply do not change the value of a company's assets, but they also change the level of damage. Higher interest rates, more represent the level of progress. Shareholders' funds increase interest rates and lower interest rates. The direction of the results of the interest rate change is already controversial [13]. The increase in interest rates due to the rise in inflation, which causes a decline in bond yields and the decline in the company's overall profitability [14].

Moreover, the increase in interest rate increases makes it difficult for the company to make a profit in a situation of high-interest rates. If interest rates reach a problematic level, insurers will struggle to meet the requirements and repay obligations. In this scenario, the company's survival may be compromised.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to examine the main factors that affect the performance of insurance companies listed on the Lahore Stock Exchange, Pakistan, in 2007-2016. The data used in this study was collected from annual reports published by insurance companies during the study period. Empirical results show that the debtor relationship is significantly negative for asset recovery, return on equity, the signing of profits and the market accounting ratio. The reverse link between demand and performance is because claims against an insurance undertaking which they have to pay to the institutions are in line with a policy that is under unregulated. Above mentioned study suggests that management is crucial to resolve any issue in the company.

Moreover, excessive requirements reduce the company's profitability, as it is more claimed that the company pays less profitable profits, thereby reducing overall profitability. Management costs are significantly negative concerning the recovery of assets, return on equity and the underwriting of profits. Incredulous relationships suggest that more than optimal management consumption harms reliable performance. Security is essential for the

return to the property. The positive link suggests that companies operating in the developed insurance market are waiting for a high level of risk, and they see insurance as a means of better diversification to save themselves from potential losses.

On the other hand, insurance is significantly negatively associated with profits. The negative link states that if insurance companies receive more insurance, they receive less money to write because it converts premiums into reinsurance companies, which ultimately deprives the available profits and creates negative effects on a solid performance.

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